

ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT, WORK-LIFE IMBALANCE, AND REMOTE PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY OF CIVIL SERVANTS IN PUTRAJAYA, MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

Remote work is becoming increasingly common in this digital era. No longer limited by space or time, this concept allows professionals to complete work from anywhere, whether at home, a cafe, or another part of the world. The flexibility offered is the main attraction, providing greater control over the balance between professional and personal life. As part of a continuous effort to improve public service delivery and to balance the needs of the job with officers' well-being, the government has agreed to establish a remote work policy as an alternative to a new way of working in the public service. Drawing on the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) theory, this study examines the influence of organizational support on the performance of remote workers. Second, examine the moderate effect of work-life imbalance on the proposed relationships. Data from 200 respondents' responses were analyzed using AMOS-SEM. The study found that organizational support significantly affects employee performance in a remote work setting. Second, work-life imbalance weakens the direct impact of organizational support on employee performance. This study shows that providing extensive work resources can motivate performance improvement even when working from home. This study suggests establishing clear organizational policies regarding boundaries for after-hours communication as well as practicing personal management strategies, such as effective time management and creating a work environment that supports work-life balance. The implications of the study findings, study limitations, and recommendations for follow-up studies are discussed at the end of this study.

Keywords: remote work, organizational support, employee performance, moderating role, public sector

INTRODUCTION

Performance is the result of work and work behaviour in completing tasks and responsibilities within a given period (Motowidlo & Kell, 2003). Performance is the quality and quantity of work results achieved by employees in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to them (Tubré et al., 2014). Performance is the level of achievement in implementing an activity program or policy in realizing the organization's goals, objectives, vision, and mission through strategic planning (Ibrahim et al., 2025; Sonnentag & Frese, 2002). The COVID-19 pandemic that occurred in early 2020 became a catalyst for significant changes in workplace performance. Social restrictions and health protocols worldwide are forcing many organizations to adopt remote work, or telecommuting, to keep operations running (Arunprasad et al., 2022). This rapid shift transformed the way millions of people work and became a catalyst for flexible working patterns (Felstead, 2022). A McKinsey and Company (2023) study found that around 70% of companies shifted to remote work during the pandemic, citing the freedom to set a more flexible work schedule. Employees can adjust their working hours to their own comfort, if they meet the responsibilities and work targets given by their employer (McKinsey Global Institute, 2023). Working from home eliminates the need to commute to work every day, thereby saving on gasoline, tolls, and public transportation costs, as well as on travel time to and from work, which can be used for more productive activities (Felstead, 2022; Leonardi et al., 2024). Many employees report being more productive when working from home because they can avoid distractions in the office, such as unimportant meetings or conversations with colleagues (Shirmohammadi et al., 2022).

Despite its many advantages, working from home also poses challenges that can affect employee productivity and well-being (Ng et al., 2022). Team management also requires a different approach, especially in ensuring clear communication, fair division of tasks, and effective performance monitoring (Azlan & Noor, 2024). Gifford (2022) found that not all employees have sufficient access to technology or a comfortable workspace at home. This can result in decreased productivity among groups that are less well-equipped in terms of infrastructure (Gifford, 2022). Factors such as Internet speed, devices that support work, and sufficient personal space to work influence the effectiveness of working from home (Mäkikangas et al., 2022). This inequality in access creates new challenges for organizations in maintaining uniform productivity standards across their employees (Noor & Nor, 2025).

The success of remote work depends significantly on the quality of management and leadership in supporting employees (Ahmad Zahran et al., 2025). Although the benefits of remote work have been widely recognized, there are still significant challenges in ensuring its long-term sustainability and effectiveness. Organizations need to evaluate various aspects, including technological infrastructure, employee well-being, and the effectiveness of communication and collaboration within teams (Amirzan & Noor, 2024; Chatterjee et al., 2022; Lim, 2023). Looking forward, the remote work trend is projected to continue to grow, reinforced by advances in collaboration technology, automation, and artificial intelligence that accelerate virtual work coordination (Becker et al., 2022; Mäkikangas et al., 2022). To succeed at working from home, employees need to be disciplined, set up a conducive workspace, and use digital tools to increase productivity. With good time management and effective communication, working from home can be a rewarding experience for both employees and employers (Pianese et al., 2023; Qi et al., 2023).

Thus, this study aims to evaluate the impact of organizational support on remote work systems on public sector employee performance. The focus of this research is to explore how the organizational support model affects employee performance; this study also aims to investigate the moderating effect of work-life imbalance. The findings of this research are expected to support better interpretation by the public sector and government in planning work policies that not only increase productivity but also uphold employees' well-being. That way, the government can develop a model that is more balanced, sensible, and responsive to employee needs and challenges in the future. This study hopes to fill some of the research gaps in previous studies. First, the topic of remote work has been widely studied in the private sector and Western contexts.

Research in the public sector in Malaysia remains limited, and working from home SSPA is now an increasingly accepted practice, especially after changes to the Civil Service Remuneration System (SSPA). This policy was created to provide government officials with the flexibility to carry out their essential duties from home, in line with efforts to strengthen productivity while not neglecting the importance of public service. The researchers found that the public sector in Malaysia is still declining. The civil service is an administrative machinery tasked with implementing government policies and providing advice and views on those policies. The purpose of the public sector is to serve people, whereas private-sector enterprises are established with profit motives. Public sector employees have job security, along with allowances, perquisites, and retirement benefits, which are not present in the private sector. In the private sector, the work environment is quite competitive, whereas in the public sector it is not, as public institutions are not established to meet commercial objectives. In addition, researchers found that studies. In addition, most studies that use JD-R theory focus primarily on job demand or job resources, and this study will focus on both. The influence of poor work-life balance as a moderator has rarely been studied. However, it has been shown to lead to severe consequences, including increased stress, anxiety, and fatigue, affecting overall mental well-being and reducing productivity and creativity, as constant stress stifles innovation. In this regard, the findings of this study assist policymakers responsible for the management and development of public sector human resources in formulating and implementing policies or intervention plans that work effectively within the public service ecosystem.

LITERATURE REVIEW

AN OVERVIEW OF REMOTE WORK

Remote work is a work model that allows individuals to perform professional tasks outside the traditional office environment, using digital technology as the primary medium for communication and collaboration (McKinsey Global Institute, 2023). Conceptually, remote work is a professional practice in which employees can work from any location outside the conventional office while remaining digitally connected to teams and organizations (Leonardi et al., 2024). The history of telecommuting can be traced back to the early 1970s, with Jack Nilles, a NASA researcher, who first introduced the term "telecommuting" in 1973. In the early days, this concept was still limited to a few specific industries and very dependent on limited communication technology (Felstead, 2022). Significant development began in the 1990s with the advent of the Internet and digital communication technologies, enabling global connectivity.

The most dramatic turning point in the evolution of remote work occurred in 2020 with the COVID-19 pandemic, which dramatically forced global organizations to adopt remote work as a business

continuity strategy (Shirmohammadi et al., 2022). Advantages of remote work include enabling employees to work from any location, reducing geographical limitations in talent recruitment, reducing office operational costs, lowering employee transportation and accommodation costs, and enabling employees to work on personal productive hours (Becker et al., 2022; Gifford, 2022; Ng et al., 2022). Disadvantages of remote work includes communication challenges, potential miscommunication due to limited direct interaction, difficulty building team bonds and organizational culture, social isolation, difficulty monitoring performance, depends on the quality of the Internet connection, requires sophisticated hardware and software, data security risks and privacy, and challenges in creating psychological boundaries (Chatterjee et al., 2022; Mäkikangas et al., 2022; Qi et al., 2023).

An inclusive understanding of remote work reveals that this model is not just a trend but a central revolution of the global work ecosystem. The success of its implementation depends heavily on the organization's and the individual's ability to manage the technological, social, and psychological complexity that accompanies it (Becker et al., 2022; Gifford, 2022). In the Malaysian public sector, the officers may choose remote work when (a) receiving instructions from the Government; (b) receiving instructions or permission from the Head of Department; and (c) making an application and obtaining approval from the Head of Department. In certain circumstances, the Chief Secretary to the Government or the Director General of Public Services may direct any officer to remote work in the interests of the service (Ma'arof et al., 2023). For officers who are instructed, permitted, or approved to work remotely, the following requirements must be met. These include always be at home or a location approved by the Head of Department as a place of work during the specified working hours; always be contactable during the working period, days and hours; always be ready to appear at the office or any other location instructed by the Head of Department within a reasonable period; and all laws, regulations, circulars and instructions in force and applicable to public officers from time to time, including, among others, but not limited to: (i) Official Secrets Act 1972 [Act 88]; (ii) Security Instructions; (iii) Public Officers (Conduct and Discipline) Regulations 1993 [P.U (A) 395/1993]; and (iv) Financial Procedure Act 1957 [Act 61].

JOB DEMAND-RESOURCES (JD-R) THEORY

Job Demand-Resources (JD-R) theory explains how jobs and resources affect job performance through employees' well-being and how employees use proactive and reactive work behaviours to influence job demands and resources (Bakker et al., 2023). The core assumption is that certain physical, social, or psychological aspects of work and the organizational environment affect employees' well-being (Bakker & Demerouti, 2024). Although all organizations are unique, their jobs may have different characteristics. The first proposition of the JD-R theory is that all job characteristics can be modeled into two categories: job demands and job resources (Granger et al., 2024). Job demands are defined as physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of jobs that require physical, cognitive, and emotional effort. On the other hand, employment resources, defined as the physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of work, have the potential to motivate, regulate the impact of job demands, and stimulate learning and personal growth (Demerouti & Bakker, 2023).

As shown in Figure 1, high job demands and high job resources are generally necessary to create jobs that are both challenging and motivating. However, they can still cause stress when demands exceed individual capacity. High job demands and low job resources are risky and can lead to work fatigue (burnout) in individuals, resulting in performance decline. On the other hand, low job

demands and high job resources can lead employees to experience boredom or underutilization when resources are not used productively (Bakker & Demerouti, 2024). Finally, low job demands and low job resources generally lead to monotonous, less challenging job characteristics, which can lower employee motivation and engagement.

According to this theory, creating a supportive culture is a fundamental resource in the workplace. It is about providing the right tools, resources, and systems that meet employees' needs in both their professional and personal lives. For example, organizations offer surveys or feedback forms where employees can voice concerns or suggestions about remote work, and they offer flexible hours or job sharing to help employees effectively balance their work and personal lives. Employers can also create a supportive environment where everyone feels safe enough to talk about mental health issues. Work-life balance is a component of job demands outlined in the theory. Although organizational support can be a valuable resource, remote work can increase several work demands, including work overload and extended working hours, technostress, a lack of face-to-face social interaction, and unclear work instructions (Bakker et al., 2023). At the same time, remote work also needs important work resources such as autonomy and flexibility, freedom to manage time and work methods, organizational support, technological support, collaboration platforms, training, and work-life balance resources (Bakker & Demerouti, 2024). Effectively balancing work and personal life can reduce stress and improve mental health.

Figure 1. Job Demand-Resources (JD-R) Theory (Adapted from Demerouti et al., 2001)

ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT FOR REMOTE WORK AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

A robust organizational culture is key to the victory of a remote work model (Azlan & Noor, 2024). Organizations need to build an environment that supports collaboration, innovation, and open communication (Ahmad Zahran et al., 2025). This fosters an atmosphere where employees feel comfortable sharing ideas and voicing their opinions. In addition, organizational leaders need to take the initiative to develop values that emphasize teamwork and mutual support (Noor & Nor, 2025). Organizations can offer mental health programs, such as online counseling sessions or webinars on coping with stress (Lim, 2023). Culture and communication are the lifeblood of the office, and these days, all of that can be digital. If the employer values openness, honesty, and a laid-back nature, with flat hierarchies and minimal micromanagement throughout the office, the same goes for the remote workforce (Qi et al., 2023). In a virtual environment, leaders need to be good listeners, empathetic, and able to address their employees' mental challenges (Pianese et al., 2023). To ensure communication and tasks can be carried out smoothly, substantial information technology support is essential to avoid technical issues that can affect the company's productivity (Chatterjee et al., 2022). Technology is the backbone of the hybrid work model's success. A variety of tools and applications have been developed to support employees in carrying out their tasks, whether in the office or from home (Mäkikangas et al., 2022). Organizations also need to ensure that all employees have access to the necessary technology and equipment (Amirzan & Noor, 2024). This includes a stable Internet connection and the right tools to get their work done efficiently. By providing the right tools, employees will feel more empowered and able to contribute positively to the organization (Becker et al., 2022; Gifford, 2022). Therefore, the following hypothesis is posited:

H1: Organizational support for remote work significantly influences employee performance.

MODERATING ROLE OF WORKLIFE IMBALANCE DUE TO REMOTE WORK

Work-life balance refers to an individual's ability to manage work responsibilities and personal life. A good work-life balance is important for employee well-being and positively impacts workplace productivity (Mäkikangas et al., 2022). According to Gupta et al. (2024), work-life balance involves effective management between work demands and personal life, and encompasses physical, mental, and emotional aspects that affect overall quality of life. Constant workload, pressure to achieve high performance, and job demands often add to stress. Mondragon and Wieland (2022) found that high stress and work-life imbalance can lead to burnout among employees. This work-life imbalance not only affects individual well-being but also seriously impacts organizational performance. High levels of stress and burnout lead to decreased productivity, increased absenteeism, and higher turnover rates (Walsh et al., 2024). By working tirelessly and regularly for hours, the employee risks mental and physical fatigue, eventually messing up all lines of life due to confusion and fatigue. Some problems include a lack of hand-eye coordination, poor reflexes, concentration issues, and the risk of accidents, injuries, responsibilities, and professional development, among other dangers of an imbalance in the work-life schedule (Raj et al., 2023). A work-life imbalance increases pressure to meet professional commitments under tight deadlines, leading employees to miss important family events such as birthdays, anniversaries, and special moments with loved ones (Vyas, 2022). Work-life imbalances can increase stress levels and increase the risk of various health hazards or lifestyle diseases such as cardiovascular disease, disrupted immune system, headaches and migraine attacks, back pain, acne, stiff muscles,

nervousness, irritability, depression, and others (Elbaz et al., 2023; Ng et al., 2022). If this difficulty is not effectively tackled, it could impede Malaysia's economic growth and weaken its standing as a viable regional investment center. Consequently, the following hypothesis is posited:

H2: Work-life imbalance moderates the relationship between organizational support for remote work and employee performance.

Figure 2 shows the conceptual model of the study. The conceptual framework for this study is based on the Job Demands – Resources Model.

Figure 2. Research Model

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted quantitatively, using a questionnaire. The questionnaire was prepared in Google Forms. The questionnaire was prepared in bilingual Bahasa Malaysia and English. The questionnaire also emphasized the confidentiality of respondents' responses. The sampling technique used was snowball sampling, identifying respondents currently serving in the public service sectors who had experience with remote work. Snowball sampling is a sampling procedure in which study respondents are asked to suggest other subjects who have characteristics suitable for the study (Noor & Fuzi, 2024). This sampling procedure is especially used when the researchers cannot obtain a list of subject names from a population with the same characteristics. In this procedure, the researchers will identify a small number of subjects who meet the study's criteria. After the subject completes a questionnaire, they are asked to name other subjects in the population with the same characteristics. This sampling method will continue until the researchers have obtained all the desired respondents. Although this sampling procedure does not involve random selection, it is suitable for use when other methods are not (Noor & Fuzi, 2024). The population of this study comprises civil servants serving in Ministries and Departments in Putrajaya. Putrajaya was chosen for this study because it is the administrative center of the federal government, with various ministries and departments that carry out their own functions in delivering services to the people. The total number of respondents for this study was 200. The sample size was appropriate for the use of AMOS-SEM to analyze the data according to Kline (2016). The researchers consider ethical issues in data collection, including protecting respondents' physical and mental well-being. Before starting data collection, the researchers explain the purpose of the research and that respondents' details will be kept confidential.

All measurement instruments used in this study to measure the identified variables were developed, tested, and validated by several previous researchers. The measurement instruments, initially written in English, were translated into Bahasa Malaysia to make the questionnaire items easier for respondents to understand. Respondents answered all questions in the questionnaire using a scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The measurement instruments for the variables of this study are shown in Table 1. According to Podsakoff et al. (2003), Common Method Bias (CMB) refers to bias arising from the similarity of the methods used to collect data. If CMB occurs, it also affects the bias in the relationship between two or more constructs in the study model. The researchers used Harman's Single Factor test method to test CMB in this study. The single factor for this study was below the 50% cutoff value (Podsakoff et al., 2003), which is 35.75%. This shows that studying is free of CMB. Data was processed using IBM AMOS software. The data analysis technique used is multivariate Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), which measures latent constructs through indicators (the measurement model) and tests causal relationships among them (the structural model).

A pilot study was conducted to determine the validity and reliability of the instrument. According to Chua (2016), the pilot study sample should range from 10 to 30 participants or not exceed 100 participants. Therefore, the researchers selected 30 samples for this pilot study. Factor analysis was conducted using the Principal Component Extraction method with Varimax Rotation of each item measuring the construct. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy measure and the Bartlett Test of Sphericity were examined prior to conducting the factor analysis. A KMO value of >0.5 (0.811) and a sufficiently large Bartlett's test of sphericity (Approx. Chi-Square=7734.002, df=825, $p=0.000$) indicate that the data meet the conditions of factorization. The total variance for measuring the factor construct is 55.76%. The results show that the number of components and the number of items per component are appropriate for measuring all constructs, as the total variance exceeds 50% (Hair et al., 2010). The pilot analysis results show that Cronbach's alpha for all variables is above 0.60, indicating that the developed items have high reliability and are suitable for use as a measurement tool (Hair et al., 2010).

Table 1. Measurement of Variables

Variables	Items	Sources
Organizational Support	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The organization does not provide clear expectations or guidance for my work when I am working remotely. 2. Organizations offer training on tools, software, or best practices for remote work. 3. The organization cares about my well-being when I work remotely. 4. There is a clear organizational policy that supports remote or flexible working in my unit. 5. The necessary technological tools (computers, software, and the Internet) are readily available for my work. 	Bentley et al. (2016), Golden et al. (2008)

Work-Life Imbalance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. I do have reliable Internet access at my workplace. 1. The demands of my work interfere with my home and family life. 2. The time my job takes up makes it difficult for me to fulfill my family responsibilities. 3. Things I want to do at home do not get done because of the demands my job puts on me. 4. My job puts a strain on me, making it challenging to fulfill my family responsibilities. 5. Due to work-related responsibilities, I must adjust my plans for family activities. 	Allen et al. (2015)
Employee Performance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Overall, I perform my job remotely very well. 2. I am a top performer compared with others in similar positions. 3. My supervisor would rate my performance as excellent even though I am working remotely. 	Koopmans et al. (2011)

FINDINGS

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILES

A total of 200 civil servants have participated in this study. As shown in Table 2, many respondents were female (n = 124, 62.0%), while male respondents accounted for 74 participants (37.0%). In terms of age distribution, most respondents were between 31 and 40 years old, accounting for 92 respondents (46.0%). This followed with 41–50 years (n=46, 23.0%), 18–30 years (n=36, 18.0%), and 51–60 years (n=26, 13.0%). Regarding work position status, more than half of the respondents were in management and professional roles (n = 138, 69.0%), while support staff accounted for 43 participants (21.5%), and 19 respondents (9.5%) held high-level management positions. Educational attainment was generally high for those holding a bachelor's degree (n = 130, 65.0%). This is followed by Diploma holders (n = 32, 16.0%), master's degrees (n = 17, 8.5%), Certificates (n = 16, 8.0%), and Ph.D. qualifications (n = 5, 2.5%).

Table 2. Demographic Profiles

Category		n	%
Gender	Female	124	62.0
	Male	74	37.0
Age	18–30 years	36	18.0
	31–40 years	92	46.0
	41–50 years	46	23.0
	51–60 years	26	13.0
Position Status	High-Level Management	19	9.5
	Management & Professional	138	69.0
	Support Staff	43	21.5
Educational Level	Certificate	16	8.0
	Diploma	32	16.0
	Bachelor's degree	130	65.0
	Master's degree	17	8.5
	Ph.D.	5	2.5

CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS (CFA)

Model fit testing is divided into three fit indices: absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices, and parsimony fit indices. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) aims to confirm whether the indicators used have a theoretical basis, thereby confirming the construct or variable. The recommended CMIN/DF value is less than 5.0 (Hair et al., 2019; Hu & Bentler, 1999). The Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI) measures the relative amount of variance and covariance, with a value ranging from 0 to 1. If the value is close to 0, the model has a low match value; if the value is small, the model has a good fit. A Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) value close to 1 indicates the model shows a perfect fit. Comparative Fit Index (CFI) ranges from 0 to 1, with values approaching 1 indicating a perfect fit. Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is a criterion for evaluating the fit of a covariance structure model, with errors approaching the population. The model is good if the value is less than or equal to 0.05; pretty good if it is less than or equal to 0.08. The CFA model shows good fit indices (CMIN/DF = 2.764, RMSEA = 0.067, GFI = 0.943, TLI = 0.952, and CFI = 0.948).

VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY ASSESSMENTS

SEM does not use Cronbach's Alpha to measure internal reliability; instead, it uses Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Each latent construct must achieve a minimum CR value of 0.70 ($CR > 0.7$) to be considered to have achieved CR (Hair et al., 2019). AVE value is also calculated using the factor loading of each item in a construct. The AVE value must reach a minimum limit of 0.50 ($AVE > 0.5$) to prove that the reliability of the measurement model of a latent construct in this study has been achieved (Hair et al., 2019; Noor & Fuzi, 2025). From Table 3, it can be seen that all AVE values have reached a minimum limit of 0.50. This shows that the construct's convergent validity has been established. Table 3 also shows that all CR values have also reached the minimum limit of 0.70. This means that the composite reliability for this construct has also been achieved.

Table 3. Items Loading, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Items	Item Loadings	AVE	CR
Organizational Support	OS1	0.749	0.583	0.893
	OS2	0.752		
	OS3	0.760		
	OS4	0.774		
	OS5	0.762		
	OS6	0.783		
Work-Life Imbalance	WLI1	0.800	0.608	0.886
	WLI2	0.770		
	WLI3	0.768		
	WLI4	0.772		
	WLI5	0.789		
Employee Performance	EP1	0.814	0.671	0.860
	EP2	0.808		
	EP3	0.835		

DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY ASSESSMENT

Discriminant validity describes the extent to which a construct does not have a strong relationship with another construct in the same model. Discriminant validity can be achieved if all diagonal matrix values are greater than other values in the row cells and in the column cells. The diagonal elements of the diagonal matrix are the square roots of the AVEs, while the values in the metric are the correlations between constructs in the model (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). As shown in Table 4, the discriminant validity is achieved.

Table 4. Discriminant Validity Results

No.	Variable	1	2	3
1	Organizational Support	0.764		
2	Work-Life Imbalance	0.411	0.780	
3	Employee Performance	0.585	0.450	0.819

Note: Values in the diagonal show the square root of AVE

MODERATION ANALYSES

Moderator variables are also related to the researcher's efforts to explain why an influence can be stronger, weaker, or even different under certain conditions. This variable adds depth to the analysis, enriching the research results and making them more meaningful. In research practice, moderator variables are often used to strengthen theoretical foundation. As shown in Table 5, there is a significant relationship between organizational support ($\beta = 0.537$, $p = 0.000$, $p < 0.001$) and employee performance. Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is accepted. If organizational support increases by 1 point, performance increases by 0.537 points. The interaction between organizational support and work-life imbalance was statistically significant ($\beta = -0.230$, $p = 0.035$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, Hypothesis 2 is accepted. This means that work-life imbalance can significantly moderate the relationship between organizational support and employee performance. A negative coefficient indicates that work-life imbalance weakens the relationship between organizational support and employee performance. As shown in Figure 3, at a high level of work-

life imbalance, the impact of organizational support for remote work on employee performance is reduced.

Table 5. Moderation Analyses

Direct effect	β	t-value	p-value
Organizational Support → DV	0.573***	5.124	0.000
Interactive effect			
Organizational Support *Work-Life Imbalance → DV	-0.230*	2.019	0.035

Note: Significance level: *** $p < 0.001$; * $p < 0.05$.

DV = Employee Performance

Figure 3. Slope Graph on the Moderating Effect of Work-Life Imbalance

DISCUSSION

The study found that organizational support significantly affects employee performance in a remote work setting. Mäkikangas et al. (2022) found that employees who work from home may experience isolation and stress. Therefore, it is important to provide emotional support. Listening to employee problems and providing moral support can increase their engagement (Becker et al., 2022; Gifford, 2022). Chatterjee et al. (2022) found that organizational support and appreciation for employees' performance are effective ways to increase engagement. Moreover, Ahmad Zahran et al. (2025) and Noor and Nor (2025) found that employees who feel they have opportunities to grow are more engaged and satisfied with their jobs. Providing access to training and online courses that can help employees improve their skills, and a positive work culture, such as collaboration, open communication, and inclusiveness, play an important role in employee engagement (Qi et al., 2023).

Second, work-life imbalance weakens the direct impact of organizational support on employee performance. Although there are many benefits from working with a remote system, it does not mean that there are no challenges in living with it. The work-life balance is becoming increasingly complex due to economic pressures, changing lifestyles, and the advancement of digital technology that blurs the boundaries between work and personal life (Elbaz et al., 2023; Raj et al., 2023). Workers are often burdened by long working hours, high performance demands, and an "always connected" culture via digital platforms, leading to physical and mental exhaustion and a lack of quality time with family (Gupta et al., 2024; Vyas, 2022). This challenge can be addressed by consistently communicating with colleagues through video calls and chat, joining communities, or finding a comfortable place to work together (Ng et al., 2022).

From the perspective of the study's contribution to theory, this study provides new insights, namely the application of the Job Demand-Resource (JD-R) theory in the Malaysian public sector, which remains understudied. The government has implemented the Work From Home policy for civil servants and government-related companies starting April 15, 2026. The purpose is to reduce fuel consumption and ensure the sustainability of the energy supply. Therefore, this study is very relevant because remote work was previously seen as an alternative and is now a necessity, especially for public sector workers. Although working from home offers various advantages in terms of flexibility and cost savings, its implementation is not without challenges. This study shows that employee productivity can be affected if employer support is lacking and a work-life imbalance occurs.

To ensure remote work can be practiced sustainably in the future, the opinions of employees at all levels who work remotely are important. In addition to employees, employers must also meet the requirements and not rely solely on personal Internet connections. The support of colleagues and management in jointly making remote work a success is seen as equally important. Coworkers can offer support by helping with completing a project and listening to a colleague's work-related problems (Walsh et al., 2024). The government must also play a role in preparing and drafting policies, guidelines, and circulars that serve as guides (Becker et al., 2022; Lim, 2023). Although remote work practices have shortcomings, the government's role in introducing tax relief facilities for Internet access and the purchase of gadgets and technological equipment, such as laptops, has reduced the burden and alleviated employees' emotional distress. In addition, more detailed policies and regulations are also needed to ensure more effective implementation of remote work (Gifford, 2022). Remote work has its own impact on workers' work-life balance. However, this impact can be stabilized with awareness and sensitivity to manage and control emotional levels (Ng et al., 2022). Thus, social support includes a variety of material and emotional aspects that are crucial. If a person receives strong social support from family and friends, they will feel better and not feel alone (Ahmad Zahran et al., 2025; Walsh et al., 2024).

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH SUGGESTIONS

This study has several limitations that affect its results. First, this study was conducted on a small sample of 200 respondents, so the results cannot be generalized. Apart from that, this is a cross-sectional study that examines the relationship between the constructs at a single point in time. Therefore, the results may not provide a comprehensive picture of the constructs studied. A longitudinal study is needed to obtain a more accurate picture and more consistent results. In addition, this study relies entirely on quantitative surveys. Therefore, to ensure the accuracy of the

data obtained, qualitative methods such as face-to-face interviews should be used to yield more accurate results. For future studies, we suggest using the same model, expanding it to include several causal factors that explain the relationship between the variables studied.

CONCLUSION

Remote work has become a dream for many people. This is because it is seen as very flexible in terms of space and time. An employee can perform work responsibilities from anywhere if the equipment and technology support his or her ability to perform the task. It is also known as an alternative work arrangement that provides employees with flexibility not only in working hours but also in balancing work and life responsibilities and in saving time commuting to and from work. The question arises as to how the employment relationship process occurs when working from home. Have the conveniences of technology and smart devices succeeded in creating harmonious and effective work? Ideally, remote work was practiced in most developed countries before COVID-19, providing opportunities to improve work-life balance. However, the question arises whether it is effective when the entire family, including children, is at home, and what the implications are for employees. This study examines the influence of organizational support on the performance of remote workers. Second, examine the moderate effect of work-life imbalance on the proposed relationships. The outcomes suggest that government and work organizations need comprehensive restructuring to make remote work a success. In addition, several challenges also need to be considered. These include maintaining employee-employer relations, work-life issues, digitalization, working time, and work organization issues. These challenges must be addressed for remote work practices to function well.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding the paper's publication.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

The authors confirm their contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: Siti Nuratiqah Shaikh Ibrahim; Nurul Hidayana Mohd Noor; data collection: Siti Nuratiqah Shaikh Ibrahim; analysis and interpretation of results: Siti Nuratiqah Shaikh Ibrahim; draft manuscript preparation: Nurul Hidayana Mohd Noor. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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